

PSYCHOLINGUISTIC RESEARCH APPLIED TO BILINGUAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS

Shokhsanam Rashid kizi Ibragimova

Humo Academy School, English teacher

Annotation: This article explores the importance of psycholinguistic approaches in bilingual environment. It discusses the contributions of key researchers in the field and highlights the importance of considering the psychological aspects of language learning and acquisition.

Keywords: Bilingual environment, psycholinguistics, foreign language learning, bilingualism, subject-centered approach, foreign language acquisition

Bilingual education is one the main elements of language education, which is acknowledged by the world trend towards integration in the economic, political and cultural spheres. Consequently, psycholinguistic approaches are necessary for the teaching of foreign languages. By the definition of R.F. Frumkina (2004), psycholinguistics is "the science of what mental processes take part in, when we generate speech, i.e. speak, listen and read, as well as how we master speech in our native language and in a foreign language". The more knowledge about the speech behavior of a person, the more effective the technique will be able to form these skills. The article is aimed at identifying linguistic and psycholinguistic approaches to the problems of interrelationship in bilingual education. The structure of the article includes the definition of the features of modern approaches of psycholinguistics in conditions of bilingual education. The materials of the article can be useful for linguists, psychologists and teachers of a foreign language.

Despite a sufficient number of studies devoted to bilingual education, the problem of determining contemporary psycholinguistic approaches remains poorly understood. Bilingual education is one of the innovative methods of teaching. The problem of teaching the second foreign language is extremely multifaceted and complex.

A psycholinguistic approach to the study of language appeared long before the scientific direction with this name was officially formalized in the middle of the 20th century. Russian psychologists and linguists A.A. Leontiev and Vygotsky can be considered predecessors of modern psycholinguistics.

Among modern researchers should be noted Zalevskaya A.A, Belyanina V.P, Frumkin R.M, Glukhova V.M, Kovshykov V.A, Zimnyaya I.A. and others, who widely considered the problems of psycholinguistics in the study of the second foreign language, as well as problems related to bilingual education.

According to A.A. Leontiev, the identification of the psycholinguistic essence of teaching foreign languages requires a clear definition of the concept of "psychological basis for intensification of teaching foreign languages" (Leontiev A.A., 1999). The three-level nature of this phenomenon (at a didactic-methodical level, in relation to the educational activity of each individual student, collectively-psychological or socio-psychological) significantly expands the field of its functioning. Actually, the psychological content is presented at the levels of the activity of the individual student and at the socio-psychological level of the intensification of educational activity. In the first case, we are talking about the orientation to different modes of perception and different types of memory, ensuring the motivation for acquiring the learning language. In the second case, this is the socio-psychological organization of the learning process (in the group), which best ensures the assimilation of the required knowledge and skills of each individual student. Analyzing the content of the foreign language acquisition approaches, A.A. Leontiev (1999) defines learning non-native language as learning a speech activity. A.A. Leontiev emphasizes the role of the cultural component in acquiring foreign language and affirms the importance of teaching the orientation in the recruitment of linguistic knowledge and knowledge about the country of the learning language in the way a native speaker performs it. This is the main task of acquiring the language in the cognitive aspect.

A.A. Leontiev considers that the ways of psychological intensification of teaching foreign languages in a brief form represent a psycholinguistic program of teaching foreign language, which is one of the foundations of his concept.

Bilingualism (or bilingualism) in the definition of the famous American linguist W. Weinreich (1979) in his book *Languages in Contact* is represented as "the practice of alternately using two languages will be called bilingualism and the person involved, bilingual" (Weinreich U., 1979).

The psycholinguistic side of bilingualism researches issues the process of acquiring a second language, the influence of the age to learning process, the ability of bilingual to shift from one language to another, how well bilinguals switch between languages, how much the typological characteristics of the two languages

matter, how difficult it can be to acquire a second language based only on one's native tongue, and how successful it is to learn a third foreign language.

Summary: Bilingual education is an increasingly popular approach to language teaching. Psycholinguistics plays a vital role in understanding the cognitive processes involved in learning a second language. This article examines the work of prominent researchers in psycholinguistics and emphasizes the need to consider the psychological factors that influence language acquisition. The article also explores the concept of bilingualism and the challenges and benefits associated with learning multiple languages.

References:

1. Brown D. (2000). *Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy*. 2nd ed. Harlow, Essex: Longman, P. 480.
2. Belyanin V.P. (2003). *Psycholinguistics*. - Moscow: MPSI. – P. 232.
3. Frumkina R.M. (2004). *Psycholinguistics: What we do when we say and think: Preprint WP6*. Moscow: State University Higher School of Economics, 2004.
4. Leontiev A.A. (1999). *Psycholinguistics in acquiring the language. Fundamentals of psycholinguistics*. - M.: Sense, - P. 218-228.
5. Mechkovskaya N.B. (2000). *Social linguistics: A manual for students humanitet. Universities and pupils of lyceums / N.B. Mechkovskaya*. - Moscow: Aspect-Press, p. 173.
6. Weinreich U. (1979). *Language contacts: the state and problems of the study*. Kiev: Vishcha school. p. 263.